

Formation Constants of Cadmium-, Copper-, Mercury-, Magnesium-, Nickel- and Zinc(II) with 4-(1-Naphthaledene)hydrazinobenzofuro[3,2-d]-pyrimidine

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The stability constants of metal complexes with a great variety of ligands have been studied. But literature reveals a lack of information on solution studies of benzofuro[3,2-d]pyrimidine Schiff bases. In view of biological importance of benzofuron derivatives¹, it was thought worthwhile to study the solution stabilities of the 4-(1-naphthaledene)hydrazinobenzofuro[3,2-d]pyrimidine with various bivalent metal ions potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH metric titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti².

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand formation constant : The values of \bar{n}_A at various pH values were calculated from the acid and ligand titration curves using Irving and Rossotti formula. The proton-ligand stability constant was calculated by plotting the values of \bar{n}_A against B . The approximate $\log pK_1^H$ value corresponding to $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$ (half-integral method) was obtained from the curve. However, the best values of that of the ligand was found from the plot of $\log \bar{n}_A/(1-\bar{n}_A)$ against B . The plot was to be linear with intercept equal to $\log pK_1^H$ and slope equal to unity³, suggesting that only one proton is dissociated. These values are recorded in Table 1.

hydrogen and hydroxyl bearing complexes and complexes with anions present can reasonably be considered to be negligible under the present experimental conditions and have been ignored. The hydrolysis of metal ion is accompanied by liberation of protons and as such displacement of metal titration curve takes place even in the absence of any reaction with the reagent. In order to avoid this error, all calculations were done below pH at which no precipitation occurred.

The values of the metal-ligand formation number \bar{n} was obtained at various pH values. The increase in \bar{n} values was continuous. The \bar{n} values were in the range $0.084 < \bar{n} < 1.9$, indicating the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. The graph of \bar{n} against pL were plotted and the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were calculated by half-integral method at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5. These values were further corroborated by plotting $\log \bar{n}/(1-\bar{n})$ and $\log (2-\bar{n})/(\bar{n}-1)$ against pL. In all these cases, values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ evaluated from the linear plots were quite well and these values are reported in Table 1.

The stability constants for various complexes were found to follows the order : $Mg^{II} < Hg^{II} < Cd^{II} < Zn^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II}$, in agreement with the Mellar and Maley order for bivalent chelates⁵.

Relationship of the stability constant with ionic/atomic parameter of the metal : The plots of $\log K_1$ of different metal ions with atomic number⁶, ionisation potential⁷, electronegativity and reciprocal of ionic radii were drawn and the results are in good agreement with that observed by earlier workers⁸.

Experimental

The ligand was synthesised by refluxing equimolar quantities of 4-hydrozinobenzofuro[3,2-d]pyrimidine (0.01 mol) and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol. The solid yellow mass obtained immediately was refluxed on a water-bath for 1 h, then cooled and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, $C_{21}H_{14}N_2O_2$, m.p. 283–85°.

All chemicals used were analytical grade. Dioxane was purified⁹ prior to use. Stock solutions of $NaClO_4$, $HClO_4$ and $NaOH$ were prepared by the usual manner in double-distilled CO_2 -free water and standardised.

The pH metric titrations were carried out at $30 \pm 1^\circ$

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL(II)-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS

Metal / Ligand		Ionic strength (0.1 M)	$-\Delta G^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹
Ligand		10.4081	—
Mg	$\log K_1$	5.0067	7.0249
Hg	$\log K_1$	6.6739	9.2282
Cd	$\log K_1$	7.6140	10.5571
Zn	$\log K_1$	9.0745	12.6106
Ni	$\log K_1$	9.4930	13.2
	$\log K_2$	6.8393	
Cu	$\log K_1$	10.0107	13.88
	$\log K_2$	9.2666	

Metal-ligand stability constant : Titration curves reveal that the metal titration curves are well-separated from ligand titration curve, indicating that as complexation with ligand takes place there is a liberation of proton⁴. Since the solutions used were dilute, the probability of existence of

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with an Elico LI-122 pH meter using glass electrode (EL-52).

Titration procedure : The experimental method of Bjerrum and Calvin as modified by Irving and Rossotti² was used to determine \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL values. The following carbonate-free solutions (total volume 50 ml, ionic strength 0.1 M NaClO₄) were titrated potentiometrically with NaOH (0.0944 M) : (1) 5 ml HClO₄ (0.001006 M) + 0.5 ml KNO₃ (0.01 M), (b) 5 ml HClO₄ + 0.5 ml KNO₃ (0.01 M) + 5 ml ligand in dioxane (0.002 M) and (c) 5 ml HClO₄ + 0.5 ml metal nitrate (0.01 M) + 5 ml ligand in dioxane (0.002 M). The ratio between the metal and the ligand was kept at 1 : 2 in all the cases.

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